

A study on The Impact of Rebranding on Customer Loyalty

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Abstract

Rebranding is one of key Marketing strategy that improve the company image from their competitor brand. This Research paper examine the impact of Rebranding on customer loyalty looking into both positive and negative results from Rebranding. This study investigates thorough knowledge of how rebranding attempt affect consumer perceptions and loyalty through a review of the body of current literature and case studies.

Keyword: *Impact of Rebranding, Customer Loyalty*

Introduction

Rebranding refers to giving an established brand a new name, phrase, symbol, design, or a mix of these in order to establish a unique position in the eyes of stakeholders. Rebranding can improve a business's market visibility and get attention of in new customer, but it also runs the danger of upsetting current loyal customer. The dynamics between rebranding and customer loyalty are investigate in this study, along with the circumstances in which rebranding can either strengthen or weaken customer loyalty.

Conceptual Framework

Customer Loyalty

Customer loyalty refers to trust of customer towards the company. As seen by regular purchases made in spite of external factors and Competitor marketing campaigns. It includes both behavioral loyalty, which is the brand's ongoing favorability, and brand Attachment, which is the brand's emotional Bond.

Rebranding

Rebranding can be classified into three types:

1. Evolutionary Rebranding: To make a small changes for rebranding.
2. Revolutionary Rebranding: To make Major changes for Rebranding such as change the a new name, logo, and general brand identity.

3. Brand Revitalization: To make extraordinary changes that give promise to better customer satisfaction.

Literature Review:

(Abdul Haseeb Tahir, 2024) Apply PRISMA technique to evaluate literature and found that there is significant effect of Brand image on shaping customer satisfaction.

Batara, Hansen & Susilo, Daniel. (2022) found that rebranding has direct and indirect impact on Customer loyalty with special reference to rebranding of Lays Product.

Charumbira, Leonard Tawanda (2022) found that Rebranding improved company image with special reference to case study of Botswana Telecommunication Corporation.

Ahmad, Okechukwu, Shaari (2022) Rebranding has no impact on brand loyalty but rebranding rebuilt the brand reputation and it has significant influence on brand loyalty. The Brand reputation act as mediator between Brand loyalty and rebranding with special reference to Malaysian Airline System (MAS).

Durmaz, Yakup & Cavusoglu, Sinan & Ozer, Ozlem. (2018) examine the effect of brand image and brand benefit on customer loyalty. They found that there is positive impact of Brand benefit on Customer loyalty.

Objective of Study:

- To compare case studies of successful and unsuccessful rebranding attempt across various Industry.
- To discover the essential elements and best practices that support consumer loyalty in rebranding campaigns.
- Develop managerial implication for brand managers on how to effectively execute rebranding strategies to maintain and improve customer loyalty.

Research Methodology

This research apply a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative analyses. Furthermore, a review of secondary data, including case studies and academic articles, provides a inclusive understanding of the topic.

Comparison of Case Studies

1. Successful Rebranding: Apple Inc.

In 2007, Apple Inc. strategically repositioned its name from "Apple Computer, Inc." to "Apple Inc." to reflect its growth into consumer electronics. The new brand identity, coupled with innovative products like the iPhone, strengthened customer loyalty by harmonizing with the advancing technological landscape and consumer preferences.

2. Unsuccessful Rebranding: Gap Inc.

In 2010, Gap Inc. reconfigured its famous logo in an attempt to rebrand. There was a lot of negative feedback from customers. Within a week, the firm had to return to its former logo since the new one was seen as a break from the brand's history and did not appeal to loyal consumers. The impact of harmonizing brand repositioning with consumer expectations and brand legacy is shown by this instance.

Determinant of the Impact of Rebranding on Customer Loyalty Authentic Communication

During the rebranding process, effective communication is a core element. Businesses must explain the main purpose behind rebranding and how it will help to enhance customer satisfaction. Retaining trust and reducing uncertainty are two core benefits of transparent communication.

Conformity with core principle

The company's commitment and basic ideology should be expressed in the rebranding. Customers are more likely to remain loyal with a brand when they confirm the rebranding is consistent with its core values.

Customer engagement

Customer loyalty may be increased by customer engagement in the rebranding process. Businesses may improve Brand Attachment and mitigate resistance to change by asking for consumer input and participating in the process.

Brand Recognition

Rebranding's negative result might be reduced by a strong established brand equity. High-equity brands can use their favorable reputation to win over customers to the rebranding effort.

Recommendations

1. Conduct extensive Market Research: To evaluate customer perception and aspiration before starting the rebranding process.
2. Facilitates Clear communication channel: To communicate clearly the purpose behind rebranding.
3. Maintain consistency between Rebranding and core values: To make confirm new brand image will reflect the core principles of company

4. Encourage Customer participation: To participate your loyal customer in rebranding process through customer feedback and participation.
5. Measure Brand value: To measure and maximize current brand equity to reinforce the rebranding attempt.

Conclusion:

Customer loyalty is highly impacted by rebranding. It may improve brand equity and customer loyalty when executed with clear communication, Consistent with core values, and consumer Engagement. However, a loss of Customer loyalty and separation from customers might result from failure from the rebranding process. Businesses must carefully plan their rebranding initiatives to make sure they appeal to both new and existing consumers.

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